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In-class Exercise 1: Informal process model

The exercise will use this natural language description of a disability insurance claim handling process.

When a claim has arrived, a junior claims officer enters the claim details into the insurance information system. The same junior claims officer performs a basic check to ensure that the customer's insurance policy is valid and that the type of claim is covered by the insurance policy. It is rare for the claim to be rejected at this stage, but it can happen, in which case the junior claims officer sends a notification to the client about the rejection.

If the claim is not rejected, the claim is marked as "eligible" and is moved to a senior claims officer who performs an assessment of the reported disability and determines the monthly benefit entitlement. In the case of short-term disability benefits, the senior claims officer performs the benefit assessment without requiring further documentation. Once a decision is made, the senior claims officer sends a notification to the customer regarding the outcome and registers the entitlement on the insurance information system.

In the case of long-term disability claims, the senior claims officer, after performing the disability assessment, requires a full medical report in order to determine the benefit entitlements. Before sending a request for a full medical report to the health provider, the junior claims officer sends the customer a request to sign a form authorizing InsureIT to request such a medical report from their health provider. Once the medical report arrives, the senior claims officer reviews the report, and then determines the monthly benefits entitlement and the rest of the process continues like in the case of short-term disability claims.

Later, after the entitlement has been registered, both for short-term and long-term claims, a finance officer triggers the first entitlement payment manually and schedules the monthly entitlement payment for subsequent months. Then, every month a payment is sent automatically to the client.

In case of long-term disability, the duration of the benefit (number of months) cannot be determined in advance when the claim is assessed. In these cases, the benefit is granted for a period of 6 months and the case is reviewed by a senior claims officer every 6 months in order to determine if the benefit should be extended. If the benefit is not extended the client is sent a notification about the termination of the benefits. Otherwise, for some benefit renewal cases a simple check is sufficient to determine the benefit entitlement and continue with the process as usual. In other cases, the senior claims officer requires a new medical report, which means that the whole process of obtaining a medical report has to be repeated, except for the letter of authorization signed by the customer.

Part 1: Tutorial

We will model the previous process using [BPMN Sketch Miner](#) (as the tool has been tested primarily with Google Chrome we advise you to use Google Chrome as well). This tool for textual modelling of BPMN processes reads a textual description of the process and produces a BPMN diagram.

Here are the basic **syntax rules** for the textual language for process modeling:

- To model a **task**, simply write down its name on one line. Write down the name of the next task that happens in the process in a new line.
- Separate different **process instances** with an empty line. A process instance is a sequence of tasks/events that happen during one execution of the process.
- State the **role** of the person executing the task followed by ":" and then the name of the task. All proceeding tasks are assigned to that role until a new role is stated. Thus, it is sufficient to state a role only when the role changes.

Role: Task

- **Events** describe interactions between the process and the external world. Include the name of the event between parenthesis.

(name of the event)

(send Message)

(receive Message)

- To state that a **task** can happen **multiple times** (i.e., in a loop) it is sufficient to repeat the name of the task twice in the sequence.

Task before the loop

Task in the loop

Task in the loop

Task after the loop

- To leave a **comment** in the text use the "///" before the text you do not want to be visualized in the model.
- To avoid repeating too many lines in your text use **fragments**. Fragments are used to list incomplete task sequences which should be attached to other task sequences.

A		A		A		A
B		B		B		B
C		C		C		C
D		D		D		D
A		...		Z		Z
B	}]			B		B
C		C		C	}]	
E		E		D		...

Fragments are task sequences which begin or end with “...” (or both). E.g., after stating the sequence of tasks in the first full process instance, to avoid repeating the initial common tasks in the second instance, write “...” followed by the last common task with the first instance and then continue describing the tasks which are different from the first sequence. If you do not know yet how an instance ends, use the “...” at the end in the instance, and define the ending later by defining an instance starting with an “...” and followed by the last task in the sequence which ends with “...” mentioned above.

Before starting with the exercise do the following tutorials in order to get yourself familiar with the tool and its language syntax:

<https://www.bpmn-sketch-miner.ai/tutorial/0-00-first-sequence.html#>

Part 2: Modeling

For this part of the exercise, based on the process description above, you will need to identify the roles of the people involved in the process, the tasks that they need to perform and any events that might be relevant for the flow of the process. Remember that you do not have to use all of the details described in the process, but only the ones relevant for identifying the items mentioned before. Also be careful when identifying the sequence of tasks to state in the process model, they may not always be in the same sequence as they appear in the process description.

Based on the in-class tutorials you did with the BPMN Sketch Miner, input the roles, tasks and events in the correct order in the BPMN Sketch Miner to visually reconstruct the process model in BPMN.

To get started, use the following link to the BPMN Sketch Miner which contains the process description broken down to paragraphs to facilitate your understanding:

<https://www.bpmn-sketch-miner.ai/tutorial/11-00-challenge-one.html#>

Deliverables:

- a) Once you are sure that your process model is complete, submit in iCorsi:
 - 1) its textual description from the BPMN Sketch Miner
 - 2) the visual process model as a PNG file (the export button is in the top right corner of the screen).

- b) Also, answer the 2 surveys starting from

<https://www.bpmn-sketch-miner.ai/feedback/student-challenge.html>

After filling in all survey questions, click the “Submit” button and then follow the link to a quick standard survey for testing the usability of the tool. When you are done click the “Submit” button again.

In-class Exercise 1: Informal process model - Solution

The following solution is one possible solution of the described process. Other solutions may be correct as well, especially in the textual model.

Textual Model – Possible solution

Junior: (receive claim)

Enter the claim

Do a basic check

(send rejection notification)

...

Do a basic check

Mark claim as eligible

Senior: Perform disability assessment

Determine benefit entitlement

(send outcome to customer)

Register the entitlement

...

...

Senior: Perform disability assessment

Require a medical report

Junior: (send authorization request)

(receive authorization)

(send medical report request)

(receive medical report)

Senior: Review medical report

Determine benefit entitlement

...

...

Register the entitlement

Finance: Trigger first entitlement

Schedule monthly payments

(send payment)

(send payment)

...

(send payment)

Senior: Review the benefit

(send termination notification)

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Senior: Review the benefit

Do a simple check

Determine benefit entitlement

...

...

Review the benefit

(send medical report request)

...